

ISLAMIC FINANCE

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Annotation: *The actions prohibited in Islamic finance in this article: RIBA, gharar i.e. uncertainty, activities i.e. many opinions about Islamic financial institutions and on gambling topics have been expressed. During the reading of the article, opinions and comments will be made about Islamic finance.*

Keywords: *Islamic finance, RIBA, gharar, Islamic Financial Institutions, IMI, futures, gambling.*

The social responsibility objectives of the Islamic financial system are based on some prohibitions and incentives. As prescribed in the Qur'an, it is said to forbid RIBA (percentage) and allow trade: "Allah has made profit from trade lawful and forbidden RIBA." It supported businesses and operations. This means that all financial transactions must represent the actual transaction or sale of goods, services or benefits. Islam has also established a moral standard that is almost common in all civilized societies of the world. The structure of Islamic finance revolves around the Prohibition of any income (riba) from debt and the legality of income. It operates any state or organization, in the event that there are laws that regulate it. A set of laws that regulate the way of life of Muslim people is Sharia. Sharia is a spiritual, moral and legal and economic system for 1500 years. Islamic finance is an economic system based on Sharia law.

RIBA is an increase that is taken from the debtor as a reward. This means profit on operations related to the transfer of money to money or the addition to the agreed price on the sale of debt to the account of the delay in payment. The Sharia banned

this because of the inconsistency in the economy. Because all transactions related to the payment of interest are strictly prohibited. Thus, it is not possible to sell debt relations with the master or at a discount, and the exchange of money or goods that are dissatisfied with money, such as gold and silver, should be equal and equal by hand.

Although the term "equal to" is clear, on the one hand, any increase means that there will be a riba, but as a business, the exchange of money should also be by hand, because otherwise a person can benefit from the money that he used. or he received without giving the value against which the other party can take advantage of. The second ban is Gharar (uncertainty). Adhering to the principles of Islamic morality, Islamic finance preserves gharar (from uncertainty). Gharar means the conclusion of a contract under conditions of absolute risk or uncertainty about the results of the contract, the nature and specification of the object or the rights and obligations of the parties. Gharar also participates in the event that there is a lack of relevant information of appropriate value or that there is uncertainty of any vital information and that there is uncertainty and uncertainty that leads to the exploitation of one of the parties. Intentional hiding of information related to dishonesty, fraud or costly is equivalent to gharar.

Islamic Financial Institutions (IMI) should not engage in any kind of trade where the results are hidden because they are not sure whether the delivery will be made or not, which is necessary to complete any real business transaction. The modern practices of traditional financial institutions and insurance companies in the futures and option markets do not correspond to Sharia due to Ghar, interest, gambling etc. unsurlari. The current stock markets are buying and selling, if cleared of these elements, so it is. it is called the stock market according to Sharia. The third type of activity that it should avoid is gambling. Gambling is involved in a number of financial transactions and traditional banking products, which should avoid it.

The first Islamic Bank was founded in Egypt in 1963 . According to the Reuters agency, today more than 300 Islamic banks and more than 200 Islamic banks operate in 67 countries of the world. The total capital of Islamic banks exceeded 2 billion US dollars. Islamic banks are much more developed in Saudi Arabia, Iraq, Kuwait, Malaysia, UAE, Pakistan, Bangladesh, Turkey.

It also operates in Germany, USA, Canada, Great Britain, France, Italy, Ireland, Leixenburg and other countries. More than 130 universities of the world are preparing personnel on Islamic Bank and finance. In particular, special courses were organized in the following most famous universities of the world . Students are studying at The Bachelor's , master's and doctoral levels. In March 2010, the first Islamic bank in qozog'istan, the first from the countries of Central Asia, received permission to conduct banking operations in al - Hilal. On August 17, 2017, Zamanbank received a license for the provision of Islamic services and began its activities. In April 2009, in Kyrgyzstan, amendments and amendments to the law of the Kyrgyz Republic "on banking and banking activities" were adopted and others. These amendments created opportunities for the application of Islamic methods of financing in traditional banks with Islamic and "Islamic window".

Traditional insurance is incompatible with Sharia due to the participation of both RIBA and (gambling). Governments, public and private sector corporations mobilize resources on the basis of lotteries and circulation, which are under the hammer of gambling and are therefore prohibited in the Islamic financial system. Current futures and option contracts, which are resolved only through price differences, are covered under gambling. Similarly, the scheme, in which investors ' money is safe and inviolable, but the prizes awarded are associated with interest from the investment collected through it, also does not correspond to Sharia due to the participation of Riba (percentage) and gambling.

Conclusion. The norm of profit in the Islamic economy-in contrast to the interest rate, it is also worth studying seriously , since a more efficient and rational

mechanism of resource allocation is a system that opposes many negative trends of the modern economy (monopolization , a sharp difference between the rich and the poor, financial crises, etc.). A number of other problems facing the Islamic finance sector can also be listed, however “complexity and problems are specific to any system”. Understanding and recognizing problems is a starting point in finding effective solutions. This makes the system itself and all of its, “structural parts” healthier. Even if representatives of the industry could solve at least part of the above - mentioned problems, this-would be a huge step forward in the development and growth of the system.

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